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Low-temperature electrolysis under intermittent operation: modeling of the impacts and experimental validation

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Abstract

Green hydrogen has progressively emerged as one of the most viable options for energy transition, addressing two key issues: offer flexibility and storage services to unlock the massive integration of renewable energies into electrical grids while decarbonizing a wide range of sectors in industry and mobility. For that purpose, the dynamic operation of electrolysis is the missing link. Indeed, the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources induces fluctuating events in the load profile, which inevitably lead to performance losses during system operation. Main impacts reported from current literature can be outlined as follows: higher specific consumption, lower hydrogen purity, performance degradation over lifetime [1] [2]. Assessing and understanding the hurdles related to the intermittent operation of low-temperature electrolyzers is crucial to improve green hydrogen competitiveness. Even though conventional technologies, especially PEM, have proven their ability to be operated dynamically, the quantitative characterization of the above-mentioned impacts remains limited to date. This work focuses on the development of tools and methodologies based on experiments and modeling aiming at exhaustively assessing key performance indicators of alkaline and PEM electrolyzers operating under intermittent conditions. A dynamic lumped performance model of a PEM electrolyzer has been developed in Aspen Plus Dynamics and validated based on real experimental data and dedicated testing protocols from a 55kW system. The characterization of these impacts may lead to the development of mitigation strategies on the design or the operation.

Keywords: *low-temperature electrolysis, intermittency, performances, characterization, modeling.*

- [1] C. Zhang, J. Wang, Z. Ren, Z. Yu, et P. Wang, « Wind-powered 250 kW electrolyzer for dynamic hydrogen production: A pilot study », *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 46, n° 70, p. 34550-34564, oct. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.08.029.
- [2] A. Weiß, A. Siebel, M. Bernt, T.-H. Shen, V. Tileli, et H. A. Gasteiger, « Impact of Intermittent Operation on Lifetime and Performance of a PEM Water Electrolyzer », *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, vol. 166, n° 8, p. F487-F497, 2019, doi: 10.1149/2.0421908jes.